

BMF CP105: Health Conditions, Climate Change Perception, Concern, and Heat Tolerance Among Older Adults

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“Kingfisher was now old. His eyesight weakened, his hearing was no longer sharp, and his health declined. In his youth, Kingfisher’s fishing skills were much better. Scientific literature indicates that he would successfully catch a fish only once in every four dives. Now, with age, his fishing efficiency had halved.”

—In “Taboo Fish”, [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How is the older adults’ health condition associated with their level of perceived heat tolerance when being at home?
- How is the older adults’ health condition associated with their level of perceived heat tolerance when being outside?
- Is the relationship between older adults’ health condition and their level of perceived heat tolerance when being at home conditional on the level of concerns regarding

climate change?

- Is the relationship between older adults' health condition and their level of perceived heat tolerance when being at home conditional on the perception of climate change's negative impacts on health?
- Is the relationship between older adults' health condition and their level of perceived heat tolerance when being outside conditional on the level of concerns regarding climate change?
- Is the relationship between older adults' health condition and their level of perceived heat tolerance when being outside conditional on the perception of climate change's negative impacts on health?

Findings from this study are expected to contribute to promoting the eco-surplus culture and sustainable development [1].

1.2. Materials

The Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) will be employed for the conceptual development of this study, while the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be utilized for statistical analysis [2,3]. The dataset comprises responses from 1050 and 1061 older adults (aged 65 and over) in Warsaw and Madrid, respectively [4]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the bayesvl R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [5].

For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16400061>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis indicates that the better health condition of older adults is associated with higher heat tolerance when they are at home. However, the positive association is alleviated as older adults become more concerned about climate change (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The estimated inside temperature limit

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps to register to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institutional email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen.**

AISDL members who have joined this project: **Quan-Hoang Vuong, Viet-Phuong La.**

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

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